

Nurses' Adherence to a Nurse-Driven CAUTI Prevention Protocol

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Background

- Catheter associated urinary tract infections (CAUTIs) are the most common type of hospital-acquired infections.
- ~450,000 CAUTIs & 13,000 related deaths occur yearly.
- \$758/CAUTI event or approximately \$340 million/year.
- Increased length of stay, morbidity, mortality, & costs.
- In 2020, 5 CAUTI events occurred at the project facility (4 in ICU).
- RN non-compliance with CAUTI prevention protocol
- Decreased patient satisfaction.

Purpose

To decrease indwelling urinary catheter (IUC) utilization rates & IUC days in the ICU by improving nurses' adherence to a nurse-driven CAUTI prevention protocol.

Results

Nurses' Barriers to the Protocol

Identified Barriers to Protocol (Nurses' Survey)	Appropriate Use	Aseptic Insertion	Appropriate Maintenance	Timely Removal	Proper Documentation
Concerns or prioritization related to patient safety issues (Falls, incontinence dermatitis)	●				
Lack/limited knowledge of the protocol	●	●			
Catheter insertion practices and customs in the ICU	●				
Lack of assisting staff during insertion		●			
Lack of awareness of aseptic insertion violation consequences		●			
Heavy nursing workload			●	●	●
Lack of time			●	●	●
Lack of a standardized patient/family education tool for patient/family education			●		
Lack of timely physician orders for removal				●	
Physicians not routinely reviewing catheter necessity during rounds				●	
Documentation prompts not available on the worklist					●

Theoretical Framework: The IOWA Model

Methods

Interventions

Pre-implementation phase

- Team formation and education
- Communication with stakeholders
- SWOT analysis
- Nurses' survey
- Pre-implementation data collection (IUC days, IUC utilization rates, adherence rates)

Post-implementation phase

- Daily IUC rounding with EB checklist
- Daily EMR chart reviews with EB checklist
- Manual IUC removal reminders
- Patient/Family education
- Ongoing communication with stakeholders & staff nurses
- Post-implementation data collection

Results

Discussion

- Most common reported barriers to adherence to the CAUTI prevention protocol included heavy workload, fear of spending more time charting, lack of timely physician order for IUC removal, & lack of time.
- Statistically significant increase in nurses' adherence to the overall CAUTI prevention protocol items (55.3%, $p < 0.001$) from 40.8 to 96.1%.
- Decreased catheter days from 519 to 406.
- No statistically significant change in IUC utilization rates (816.04 vs 816.9, $p = 1.000$).
- COVID-19 surge associated increase in patient acuity, IUC use, IUC days, hospital length of stay, & nurses' workload → no change in IUC utilization rates despite a statistically significant increase in RN's adherence to the protocol.

Recommendations

- Implementation of initiatives designed to improve catheter care awareness (EMR alerts, reminders, stop order) to signal IUCs maintenance and timely removal.
- Use of tools that facilitate handoff and interdisciplinary discussions on CAUTI prevention practices.
- Routine provision of CAUTI prevention education to patient/family after IUC insertion.
- Annual nurses and physicians education on IUC risks, indications, CAUTI prevention protocol, and practices.

Limitations

- Project Implemented only on one unit. May not be applicable to other settings.
- Short duration of the project (2 months) due to COVID-19 pandemic surge.